

THE RISE OF FAR-RIGHT LEADERSHIP IN CHILE AND LATIN AMERICA: REGIONAL AND GLOBAL EFFECTS

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SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The election of José Antonio Kast as Chile's president signals a possible alignment with a growing cluster of far-right governments in Latin America. This shift may reshape regional cooperation, test Chile's traditional commitment to multilateralism, and limit the autonomy of Latin American countries, considering the growing US-China great power competition and the new US "Donroe Doctrine". While Chile's economic ties with Europe are likely to remain stable, political differences may arise over democracy and global governance. For the EU, the challenge will be to maintain pragmatic cooperation with Chile while supporting democratic institutions and sustaining regional dialogue.

Latin American governments should promote regional dialogue to address shared challenges such as organised crime,

migration, climate change, and economic resilience. Monitoring of democratic backsliding should be strengthened through exchanges of human rights institutions, electoral authorities, and civil society. EU institutions and member states should maintain pragmatic cooperation with Chile on trade and security, while separating the democracy and human rights dialogue from executive-level volatility. This can be achieved by deepening engagement between parliamentarians, regional authorities, and academic institutions, which would ensure a more resilient and multi-layered partnership. Further, the EU should support Chile and other Latin American states in diversifying their relations considering the US-China great power competition and the Donroe Doctrine.

INTRODUCTION

José Antonio Kast assumed the Chilean presidency on 11 March 2026 for a four-year period after defeating Communist Party candidate Jeannette Jara in a second-round runoff with 58% of the vote.¹ His campaign was built on topics of public fears over immigration, violent crime, and insecurity, while promising economic reactivation through radical deregulation and cuts of public spending. During his political life as a right-wing hardliner, Kast has defended the authoritarian legacy of Augusto Pinochet (1973–1990), emphasised traditional conservative values and advocated a deeper neoliberal model.

Before taking office, Kast visited a series of countries to meet with leaders and groups who he saw as his ideological peers and potential allies. He also met Javier Milei (Argentina), Daniel Noboa (Ecuador), José Jeri (Peru), Nayib Bukele (El Salvador), and the left-leaning leader Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva (Brazil) at the International Economic Forum in Panama.² Beyond Latin America, he joined Donald Trump at the “Shield of the Americas” summit in Florida, which produced the “America’s Counter-Cartel Coalition (ACCC)” to tackle organised crime, drug trafficking and immigration,³ and discussed external interference in the Americas region.⁴ Previously, he met with Viktor Orbán and Giorgia Meloni along with European far-right groups such as the European Conservatives and Reformists and Patriots for Europe.⁵

As such, foreign policy was not part of his electoral campaign except for the issue of immigration, which he used for domestic mobilisation. However, Kast’s recent visits to the US and European and Latin American countries pose questions on Chile’s likely foreign policy approach, as well as on the effects of a new far-right president for the Latin American region and the global level. In fact, these engagements suggest an emerging ideological alignment and coordination with other far-right leaderships across Latin America and the articulation of a faithful ally role for Chile in regard to the US of Donald Trump.

We argue that Kast is likely to test Chile’s traditional multilateral approach, favour selective alliances with like-minded leaders and prioritise US alignment with direct implications for regional cooperation, but without substantial trade risks for Latin America and Europe.

CHILE AS A FOREIGN POLICY ACTOR

Chile has been an active international actor since its return to democracy in 1990. Its successive governments consolidated a stable set of foreign policy roles. Chile positioned itself as a democratic advocator and promoter in multilateral institutions, given its authoritarian past. It also adopted a global free trader role as the cornerstone of its international insertion. Chile built one of the world’s most extensive FTA networks, which includes advanced agreements with the EU and EFTA. In recent years, this strategy has shown priority for the Asian region, with China as Chile’s current main trading partner. Chile’s strategy of “open regionalism” allowed it to deepen regional integration while retaining full autonomy over its trade policy, and hence also flexibility in managing its external economic relationships. It avoided full MERCOSUR membership to preserve its independent trade negotiations and tariff flexibility, opting instead for associate status in

the organisation. Politically, it participated in CELAC and UNASUR while economically, it favoured flexible platforms that aligned with its global trade strategy such as the Pacific Alliance.⁶

These roles, along with key principles such as the defence of international law and sovereignty, have shaped Chile's external identity and reinforced a domestic consensus among policymakers about its unique approach to global engagement. Multilateral economic institutions reinforced this image of uniqueness by presenting Chile as a model of economic governance.⁷ Moreover, foreign policy continuity has predominated across its left and right governments despite some nuances across different presidents. In fact, one of the main formal innovations came under Kast's predecessor Gabriel Boric (2022–2026), as he adopted a Feminist Foreign Policy. Yet this initiative complemented rather than replaced established foreign policy principles.⁸

However, Chilean foreign policy has become more politicised in recent years due to domestic fragmentation and polarisation. For instance, then-President Boric relied on traditional pillars of Chile's foreign policy such as respect for international law, sovereignty, and non-interference when taking positions on crisis situations. Yet, he has become more publicly vocal and at times used hard rhetoric in regard to international matters. He criticised Israel's actions in Gaza, condemned Venezuela as a dictatorship, challenged far-right leaders regionally and criticised Donald Trump. Tensions intensified around the U.S. actions in Venezuela when Maduro was removed from power, the US visa revocations for Chilean ministers on the grounds that they were negotiating with China over an undersea cable, and the recent war in Iran. Although all these events have been framed under traditional principles of respect for international law and sovereignty, Boric's positions have been portrayed by his domestic opponents, including José Antonio Kast, as ideologically driven and thus as undermining Chile's national interest.

Hence, Kast will also govern in a growingly polarised domestic, regional, and international context. In fact, one week before taking power, Kast walked away from a bilateral meeting with President Boric to coordinate the transition from one government to the other over the issue of China's undersea cable to connect Chile and China.⁹ He has signalled his closer ideological alignment with the US under the new "Donroe Doctrine"¹⁰ and also with various far-right governments in Latin America and Europe. Such positioning could test Chile's traditional pragmatism, particularly regarding China, its largest trading partner, in the context of the growing great power competition between the US and China. The key question is whether Kast will keep the traditional roadmap provided by Chile's established roles or seek to redefine them along more conservative and far-right ideological lines.

THE FAR-RIGHT REGIONAL LANDSCAPE: LATIN AMERICA

José Antonio Kast's presidency arrives at a moment when far-right leaderships are reshaping the political landscape across Latin America, which, only a few years ago, witnessed a resurgence of left-wing governments under the "pink tide" banner. His electoral victory and subsequent diplomatic engagements signal the consolidation of a *de facto* ideological axis that spans from Argentina under Javier Milei to El Salvador with Nayib Bukele, Ecuador

led by Daniel Noboa, Paraguay with Santiago Peña, and president-elect Laura Fernández Delgado of Costa Rica.

This far-right leadership group is characterised not only by a shared commitment to security, migration control, and economic deregulation – priorities that mirror Kast’s own campaign pledges – but also by a vocal defence of traditional conservative values. Many of these leaders have positioned themselves as bulwarks against what they decry as the excesses of “gender ideology” or “woke” policies and frame their agendas as a return to order and family values.¹¹ In Argentina, Milei has sought to ban gender-affirming care for minors and faced wide opposition from LGBTQ+ communities for his related comments,¹² while in El Salvador, Bukele upholds a total abortion ban that has led to prison charges for women affected by the law.¹³ Chile, which brought forward progressive legislation on reproductive and LGBTQ+ rights,¹⁴ could move in a different policy direction as well. One indicator for this is the appointment of Judith Marín as gender equality minister, as she has publicly decried bills to decriminalise abortion.¹⁵

Likewise, these far-right leaders have championed policies that prioritise domestic order and market liberalisation at the risk of democratic erosion and backsliding. The ideological convergence among them is not merely rhetorical. For instance, Bukele’s controversial “iron fist” approach to crime has been praised by Kast, who has similarly pledged to adopt hardline measures to address Chile’s perceived rise in insecurity. In fact, he visited El Salvador’s CECOT prison in January 2026 to assess whether Bukele’s security approach can be used as a model for his own. Economic policy alignment and similarity between them are also expected. For example, Kast’s advocacy for deregulation and public spending cuts at least rhetorically resembles the neoliberal therapy implemented by Milei in Argentina.

The far-right leaders in Latin America also share a value-driven vision of the international order, one that is deeply sceptical of multilateral institutions and global governance structures. While they do not reject cooperation outright, they criticise how certain international institutions, such as several UN agencies, erode state sovereignty and are instrumental to what they perceive as an undesirable global elite. If Kast follows the playbook of his regional ideological peers, Chile could see a sidelining of progressive policies, such as Boric’s Feminist Foreign Policy, an erosion of norms concerning democracy, human rights and gender and an overall shift toward a more partisan and ideological foreign policy with a nativist and conservative flavour. This would not only undermine Chile’s reputation as an international actor, democracy promoter and multilateral facilitator, but also weaken even more the already problematic patterns of Latin American regional cooperation inasmuch as ideological positioning and blocs of left and right will erode even more an already lost collective ability to address shared regional security and political challenges.

GEOPOLITICS UNDER GROWING COMPETITION AND POPULISM

Kast’s presidency will also be an additional test for Latin America’s position in the broader geopolitical landscape of the competition between the US and China. In fact, Chile has always aspired to be a bridge-builder between South America and the Asia-Pacific region

since the mid-1990s. The Pacific Alliance regional group – one of whose intellectual founders is Chile – not only prioritised intra-trade amongst its members but also sought to coordinate their members' trade capacities towards the Asian region, especially towards China.¹⁶ China is, for example, a key investor in Chilean mining industries. In other words, the ideological alignment with the US under the “Donroe Doctrine” risks that there will be potential political and economic costs for Chile’s relationship with China. Chile is already feeling the constraints of ongoing demands from the US to prioritise their relationship over that with China.

The far-right leaders in both Peru and Argentina have experienced similar demands from the US to reduce their economic ties with China in key strategic areas. Specifically, the US expressed concerns about Peru’s concession of a private port to Chinese investors possibly compromising Peru’s sovereignty and even hemispheric regional security¹⁷ while it has also asked Argentina to reduce its economic dependency on China.¹⁸ Yet, both actors have so far managed the US rhetorical demands as the US does not provide concrete incentives for them to reduce their economic dependency on China, and thus they have not taken any further action against China. Trump’s administration has also threatened additional tariffs for members or associates of the BRICS, where Brazil is a key member, since it sees the BRICS as detrimental to the US interest. At the moment, any policy targeting the BRICS or the trading relationship with China has been kept at the rhetorical level without any implementation of concrete sanctions. Thus, China’s involvement and economic footing pose a dilemma and a risk for both Kast and the rest of far-right leaders in Latin America as the US unfolds and puts in practice its new national security strategy.

Moreover, Kast’s foreign policy may contribute to the ongoing erosion of multilateral institutions. For instance, his posture of support to the US military action in Venezuela,¹⁹ which goes against Chile’s principle of respect for international law, not only shows his personal scepticism toward rules-based international practices but could also lead Chile to sideline forums that do not align with his conservative agenda. Two prominent examples of far-right leaders going against multilateral institutions are President Jair Bolsonaro from Brazil questioning the provision of public goods by the UNFCCC (the UN Body for Climate Governance) and the WHO, and Argentina withdrawing from the WHO and COP29. Most recently, the US also withdrew its memberships from various UN agencies.

A pattern of distance or apathy or even an instrumental or transactional approach to multilateralism would mean a change in Chile’s post-1990 identity as an active actor and supporter of global governance. This would also reflect choices of high-ranking diplomatic personnel. While the Boric government has nominated left-leaning former president Michelle Bachelet as candidate for the UN Secretary General role with the support of Brazil and Mexico, Kast has been rather silent on his support.²⁰ This ideological division between Kast and Bachelet could affect the candidature of the latter to the UN post, and it may also amplify the viability of the Argentine candidate Rafael Grossi, who is backed by President Milei, who has approached the US for support in this.²¹ Alternative venues of cooperation outside the UN institutional framework could be an option for Kast. One example of such a venue is Trump’s newly established Board of Peace, which includes Argentina, El Salvador, and Paraguay, although Chile has not officially been invited to join yet.

Accordingly, the most likely and high-impact risks stem from Kast’s alignment with US demands to reduce economic ties with China, which could strain Chile’s strategic position

as a bridge between Latin America and the Asia-Pacific. Plausible but manageable risks in this regard include the erosion of Chile's multilateral engagement, which could take the form of a withdrawal from or sidelining of forums or UN bodies. While such moves would mark a departure from Chile's foreign policy identity, economic pragmatism (e.g., maintaining EU trade relations) may mitigate its ideological extremes. The related low-probability but high-impact contingencies involve Chile's potential participation in alternative US-led coalitions (e.g., Trump's Board of Peace), which could further polarise regional dynamics and isolate Chile from its traditional partners. Policymakers should prioritise monitoring US-China tensions and multilateral disengagement as core risks, while treating speculative shifts (e.g., Chile joining new alliances) as secondary but strategically significant scenarios.

For Europe, Kast's presidency creates challenges while it keeps continuity in the relationship with Chile. Chile and the EU have recently modernised their existing FTA, in place since 2003, through the negotiation of an Interim Trade Agreement (ITA) and an Advanced Framework Agreement (AFA). The ITA has been operational since 2025 and will be replaced by the AFA once it is ratified by all EU members. Beyond the removal of tariff barriers, it also includes provisions on labour standards, environmental protection, and gender equality. While many of these provisions contrast with Kast's agenda, Chile's export-driven agenda suggests that it will prioritise pragmatic engagement over ideological confrontation in its relations with the EU. Kast is unlikely to abandon the EU relationship; instead, he may adopt a "separate tracks" policy, which would maintain the trade cooperation across the political spectrum and reserve his value-driven rhetoric for interactions with like-minded conservative European partners. This approach would mirror the behaviour of other right-wing governments in Latin America, including Milei's Argentina, where economic pragmatism has largely tempered ideological clashes. While Kast's alignment with Trump-style policies could create tensions in multilateral forums, the EU-Chile relationship is not likely to experience change and become politicised as part of Chile's foreign policy.

In the next few years, the EU should prioritise three key areas in order to navigate Kast's presidency. First, it is important to accelerate the ratification and implementation of the AFA to cement the pragmatic cooperation on trade and trade-related issues. Second, it is key to strengthen parliamentary and subnational ties with Chilean and Latin American legislators, regional governments, and civil society groups beyond the executive level. Third, the EU should engage Chile to work together within a multilateral framework and in this way provide an alternative to Chile beyond great power-dominated groupings. All these pillars can help the EU to mitigate risks of ideological drift while preserving strategic continuity in the EU-Chile relationship.

SUMMARY

José Antonio Kast's election reflects the rise of far-right governance in Latin America, with potential consequences for regional dynamics and Chile's long-standing multilateralism. His presidency could prioritise alignment with the US and amplify tensions amid the US-China competition and the "Donroe Doctrine" hemispheric approach. While the EU-Chile economic relations are expected to remain stable, divergences over democratic norms and global governance may emerge. For the EU, the priority will be to balance the pragmatic

engagement with Chile with upholding support for democratic institutions and fostering an inclusive regional dialogue.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

- *Accelerate trade ratification and implementation*
EU member states should swiftly advance the ratification of the AFA to deepen the pragmatic cooperation on trade and trade-related issues, which benefits both Chile and the EU in these economically challenging times. Accordingly, the ratification and implementation of the EU-MERCOSUR Partnership Agreement should be key, and the agreement should be prioritised as a tool to deepen the cooperation between both sides.
- *Europe's diplomatic and political engagement in Chile*
EU institutions and member states should strengthen the engagement beyond the executive level by expanding the cooperation with Chilean parliamentary groups (e.g. through the Euro-Latin American Parliamentary Assembly), regional authorities, civil society, and academic institutions. A broader diplomatic engagement will help maintain a long-term policy dialogue on democracy, human rights, and sustainable development.
- *Civil society as a brake on democratic backsliding*
Civil society organisations in Chile and across Latin America should strengthen regional safeguards against democratic erosion by institutionalising cooperation with national human rights institutions and electoral authorities. Regular exchanges and monitoring platforms across civil society organisations can help identify early warning signs of democratic backsliding and protect fundamental rights across the region.
- *Regional cooperation and multilateral governance in Latin America*
If ideological fragmentation across the Latin American region increases, European diplomacy can play a constructive role in depolarising and promoting cooperation on issues such as organised crime, migration, climate change, and economic resilience, areas where regional dialogue and coordination remain key.
- *Geopolitical balancing in the region*
Latin American countries, including Chile, should be provided with alternative options in order for them to maintain diversified international partnerships and prevent themselves from being drawn into exclusive geopolitical alignments. In this regard, the EU and European states can help promote an open economic cooperation and rules-based international engagement beyond binary US-China alignments, while supporting active strategic autonomy and pragmatic diplomacy in the region.

ENDNOTES

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